

EXPLORING THE POTENTIAL KEY FACTORS TO ANALYZE THE IMPACT OF AI IN BUSINESS DECISION MAKING

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Abstract

Artificial intelligence (AI) plays a crucial role in business decision making while impacting the firm wide performance, organizational processes and overall reputation. This study explores the potential of AI as advance technological tool in transforming the strategic decision making thus enhancing the business outcomes. A systematic protocol has been followed for selection of relevant literature by utilizing the renowned search engines like Google Scholar and IEEE Xplore to identify the high quality published studies. After a thorough literature survey it has been assessed that AI significantly contributes to financial outcomes, productivity and sustainability thus driving a substantial business growth and adaptability. AI also influence the organizational reputation by shaping the customer' trust but transparency is prior condition in AI driven systems which can be ensured by understanding the technical aspects of AI. Conclusively AI act as a powerful catalyst in decision making while delivering the measurable improvements, innovation and highlighting the critical need for transparency and trust to ensure the overall sustainability.

INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence has evolved as a substantial tech tool to boost productivity in every field by generating accurate conclusions based on the availability of large data, which is difficult to analyze manually, thus majorly transforming the approaches of business decision-making (Chintala & Thiyagarajan, 2023). AI is widely used across multiple industrial and business domains to

collect, analyze, and organize huge amounts of data. AI-based data-driven solutions, such as predictive maintenance and intelligent customer service at the corporate and industrial levels, are not only improving the decision-making capabilities but also helping businesses to hold a strong position in the competitive market of the 21st century, where consumer needs rapidly shift

in a consistently varying environment (Kaggwa et al., 2024). Thus, AI insights play a crucial role in making well-informed and quick data-backed solutions, complying with the market demands in real time more effectively and efficiently (Schmitt, 2023).

Conventional decision-making strategies are time-consuming and confined, as they majorly rely on the manual handling of data, with the utmost probability of human error, which becomes totally unrealistic in today's mega corporate and industrial sectors, where continuously varying market trends demand quick decisions based on the consumer's requirements (Schmitt, 2023). This is where AI plays its part as it accurately maps the data's patterns, and rapidly predicts the future trends, and successfully uncovers those statistical business insights that traditional analytical tools often miss (Jarrahi, 2018). AI not only boosts the decision-making process in business but also supports human planning, which is very crucial for any business to stay competitive in today's evolving global market (Paschek et al., 2018; Schmitt, 2023).

Although there is much literature available unveiling the technical capabilities of AI, despite the integration of AI in the business domain, there is limited knowledge available on this (Sharma et al., 2022). Lack of availability of factual literature about the impact of AI in the business domain emphasizes that there is still vast room available to work on this matter to bridge the knowledge gap in this regard (Edwards et al., 2000). The main objective of this study is to identify and explore those factors that play a key role in the successful adoption of AI and its substantial impact on the overall business performance. This study will help in assessing how AI has redefined the competitive strategy in business.

The main objective of this study is to identify and explore those factors that play a key role in the successful adoption of AI and its substantial impact on the overall business performance. This study will help in assessing how AI has redefined the competitive strategy in business. Moreover, it will help in generating a comprehensive overview of AI's influence in modern business practices and create a roadmap for the successful adoption and

the correct assessment of AI's potential in this domain. Briefly, this study will cover the knowledge gap between the technical capability and strategic application of AI, offering practical recommendations for industrial leaders to align with the organizational goals.

This article successfully elaborates the contribution of this amazing innovative technology while mentioning some real-world frameworks that are likely to improve strategic business performance and quick decision-making by utilizing the huge available data, thus providing actionable implications. These observations will impact a wide range of business practices and management methods from academic, conceptual, and theoretical viewpoints.

1. LITERATURE REVIEW

Artificial intelligence in the business domain has emerged as a substantial strategic asset to transform the way of making well-informed data-driven choices (Di Vaio et al., 2020). It is evident from different research studies that artificial intelligence is not only helping business leaders with better decision-making but also has a strong impact on organizational policy making, thus better complying with consumer choices and consistently increasing market competitiveness (Akhtar et al., 2019; Di Vaio et al., 2020). AI-based decision making has become critical in handling the large datasets, identifying patterns and automating repetitive tasks, guiding the strategic decisions (Al-Surmi et al., 2022).

Mega business sectors such as healthcare, finance and retail are increasingly recognizing and adopting AI to improve their market competitive strategies (Javaid, 2024a; Lysaght et al., 2019). However, these rapid uptakes raise questions that how AI's practical applications align with the theoretical models and which factors drive its' impact across different industrial sectors.

Technical aspects of AI have been extensively explored, and a wide variety of published literature is available in this regard, but its' implications in business contexts are still emerging (Lee et al., 2019). Currently available literature mainly focuses on certain specific applications such as customer relationship management, operational

efficiency and predictive analytics, but a comprehensive review of AI's impact in identifying industry-specific drivers and decision-making is still undermined. This gap is due to the lack of practical insights in to the factors substantially influencing AI's adoption, implementation success and long-term outcomes in varying business contexts (Burgos, 2024).

AI's adoption in business decision-making depends on several key factors such as data availability, organizational culture, technological readiness, and regulatory environment (Kurup & Gupta, 2022). Research shows that firms with strong leadership and data infrastructure are more likely to adopt AI. Moreover, AI-based decision making is strongly associated with improved speed, accuracy and adaptability, which are critically important for the industries undergoing rapidly growing environments (Heimberger et al., 2024). Outcomes vary across different sectors but commonly include improved accuracy, cost saving, customer engagement strategies and strong market positioning (Chen, 2019). For example, in the healthcare sector, AI assists in treatment planning, diagnostics and smooth running of hospital management systems, while in finance, AI enhances personalized services and precise fraud detection (Javaid, 2024b).

AI research in business decision making is based on several fundamental theories such as resource based view (RBV) (Stecher et al., 2020), Technology organization environment (TOE) framework (Chatterjee et al., 2021) and institutional theory. A TOE framework helps in understanding that how environmental and organizational factors influence the modern technology adoption whereas RBV theory emphasizes on leveraging the AI as a new state of the art technological competitive source to be adopted (Chatterjee et al., 2021; Stecher et al., 2020). Research methodologies varies from surveys and case studies to data analytics and experiment, still there is room for more rigorous and thorough studies to be accomplished so that the knowledge gap on the adaptability of AI may be abridged properly in business' context.

Several business sectors such as healthcare, finance and retail are leading in terms of the successful

implementation of AI with significant advancement. In Finance AI is vastly used for real time data analysis, risk assessment, algorithmic based trading and fraud detection whereas in healthcare AI assists in personalized medication, diagnostics and decision making based on data analysis. Similarly, retailers use AI for customer insights, personalized recommendations and data management allowing them to improve overall operational efficiency and customer experience (Javaid, 2024a; Sharma et al., 2022; Stecher et al., 2020). It is the need of the hour to take the AI as system's ability in any domain to perform multiple tasks intelligently and interpret the big data to successfully achieve certain objectives through flexible configuration. AI is flexible enough to accommodate the mega concepts of internet of things (IOT) and big data. IOT assists in external data acquisition as an input for AI while the term big data has been used for the data collected by other means. AI based intelligent systems are capable to generate human like behaviors including emotional, cognitive and social intelligence. Despite of all these advancements still there is an aim to create, manage and provide sound knowledge base to improve the existing intelligent systems, products, experiences and services through an optimal solution. AI is a continuously evolving technology and it is difficult to predict what impact will AI induce in futurespecially if we talk about the business domain. In this context it can be concluded that AI has not just changed the way of managing and use the information in decision making but it has also revolutionized the methods of doing business thus clearly influencing the management and trade practices along with sustainable and competitive services. Standard management systems have become efficient and flexible enough to help managers to make right decisions by the integration of AI algorithms and human intelligence. It has been reported through various published studies that these mathematical models have organized and catalogued the information data sets so well that systems' incorporated with these models are working more efficiently than human decisions. In this context an AI model of skills need development, innovation management

and leadership for business managers was proposed by Sousa & Rocha in 2019.

It is obvious that this trend will help mega corporate sectors to develop a sound connection between innovation & sustainability with the aim of incorporating the AI in business decision making, this also aligns with the United Nations' (UNs) agenda of sustainable development growth (SDG) to be achieved till 2030. This vision has collectively forced the business to adopt intelligent systems for decision making while balancing social, economic, and environmental dimensions as well. This article unveils the fact that how AI incorporated intelligent decision making helps in developing sustainable business models (SBMs). More precisely this article investigates that knowledge management systems (KMS) contribute in designing the SBMs through fueling the cultural drift which considers AI a capable tool for redefining the operational and decision making processes. The main objective of this study is to explore the potential of AI in business decision making to comply with the goal of sustainable business models along with intelligent knowledge management systems.

This study is an effort to assist the policy makers and practitioners in understanding the importance of AI in business decision making. Thus, this article significantly contributes to the literature and abridges the knowledge gap by providing the valuable insights into AI & decision making. Rest of the paper is structured as follows. **Section 3** provides a theoretical framework for AI in business decision making, **Section 4** describes the method used to conduct the research and software used for data analysis. **Section 5** presents the key findings of this study and **section 6** explains the conclusion **Section 7** discusses the future scope of the study revealing the theoretical and practical insights of the study obtained.

2. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK.

Incorporation of AI in decision making presents a transformative shift in organizational strategy, approach, innovation and operations. This theoretical framework discusses interdisciplinary concepts from cognitive psychology and theories based on technological adoption to evaluate the

role of AI in enhancing the quality, adaptability, efficiency and decision making. In this context there exist a Rational Decision Making Model (RDM) in which AI provides data driven insights and reduces the cognitive biases. AI enables the managers to analyze vast amount of data quickly thus aligning with the Herbert Simons' concept of bounded rationality by overcoming the human limitations in data processing. Technology Acceptance Model (TAM) states that factors like trust, familiarity and readiness significantly influence the adoption of AI. Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology (UTAT) theory is an expansion of TAM which states that inclusion of different organizational factors like social influence, and support systems influence that how much AI improves the overall performance.

Businesses are complex systems where multiple sections operate together. AI plays its role in integrating all these sections, identifying the patterns and effectively optimize the processes in finance, marketing and supply chain. Feedback loops in AI also enable learning over time thus continuously improving the decision making models. While discussing the role of AI in business it is obvious that AI collects data from multiple structured sources such as spreadsheets, emails and media and uses the techniques like natural language processing to track the relationships and future trends by predicting the market competitiveness, customer behavior, demands and associated risks. These predictions help the business perform smoothly and reduce the uncertainty. AI simulation assist the businesses in testing different strategies and consider best possible outcomes thus enables the decision makers to select best option quickly in competitive and uncertain situations. AI driven data insights automate the everyday tasks and provide the quick alerts for unusual situations. For example AI driven dashboards in logistics and finance help the managers to make accurate decisions quickly.

However, it is very important to make the AI models trained so well to generate accurate results on any associated external data. This level of accuracy can be achieved implementing the optimizing techniques which make the AI models

efficient enough to learn the data patterns accurately on any new unseen data. Incorporation of AI in decision making should consider the accountability, data privacy and social responsibility strictly via strong guidelines to ensure the ethical use of AI in business domain. Briefly AI plays crucial role in improving the decision making process in business. It helps in processing the big data, predict trends and support human judgement. However businesses must address the associated challenges as well such as over reliance, ethical use, and biasedness to completely benefit from AI to achieve the targets.

3. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study has been conducted in five different stages following the structured method for systematic literature review to ensure that all the relevant literature within selected time frame has been included in this analysis. First a review protocol was developed to which highlighted the choice, phrases and structure of key words. Second an inclusion and exclusion criteria was established for the relevant publications to filter literature of interest for our study. Third the papers were searched based on the pre defined phrases and keywords. The articles found in the search process were critically analyzed before performing the data extraction and synthesizing final findings. Fig 1. Describes the complete stages of finding the relevant literature for this study (see Fig 1).

• Protocol Development

This systematic literature study started by developing a protocol following the method of Cochrane handbook for systematic reviews of intervention (Higgins & Green, 2008). In this protocol development process the main target was to establish the research questions along with the research strategy, inclusion-exclusion and quality assessment criteria. The following research questions motivated the overall review process:

- What are the key factors impacting the adoption of AI in business decision making?.
- What are the modern trends in integrating the AI across various sectors ?
- What are the long term outcomes of adopting AI in decision making process and

overall organizational competitiveness?

- How businesses can utilize AI driven statistical insights to optimize the organizational process and strategies?

These research queries established the basis for deciding how to proceed in the next phases of the study, which data sources and sets of keywords are to utilize.

• Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

A number of inclusion-exclusion criteria were applied to set the boundaries for this systematic literature study. Selected studies were included if they focused on how the AI can contribute in business value by automating the process of decision making or how AI can be adopted and utilized effectively in organizational context. The studies more focused on the technical aspects of AI such as implementation of machine learning or deep learning models and mathematical modeling of AI architectures were considered out of scope of this study. Only publications since 2015-onwards were selected as the implementation of AI at organizational level have become common since last decade. Studies not written in English were also excluded from this review. Additionally, the study also included conference proceedings and journal articles. However, book series, reports, dissertations and other studies which were not peer reviewed were excluded.

• Data Sources and Search Strategy

The first step in the search strategy was to form search strings. Two distinct sets of key words were formed. In the first set all the keywords related to AI associated technologies were included and second set was composed of the keywords relevant to organizational perspective. Keywords (Table 1.) from both the sets were combined to create a long, final search string. These search strings were applied to different search engines such as Google Scholar and several other electronic databases such as IEEE Xplore, Scopus and web of knowledge. This step was performed to ensure that all the relevant articles have been indexed. The data collection procedure started from October 15 2024 and concluded on November 20, 2024.

• **Quality Assessment**

All the selected articles were thoroughly checked to assess the eligibility and quality. Studies were examined in terms of credibility, relevance and scientific rigor. Scientific rigor refers to the implementation of an appropriate research method to ensure the quality of study. Credibility refers to the proper, and authentic published data which can be referred in the study being composed. Relevance refers if the findings are relevant to the topic of interest for example in this study all those articles focused on organizational and academic community engaging in AI projects were targeted. The quality criteria if properly followed ensure that article after passing this process are likely to compose a valuable

contribution to this study. Conclusively 45 published studies were finalized for data extraction and composition after this stage.

• **Data Extraction & Synthesis of Findings**

To synthesize and organize findings from various studies a concept matrix was developed. This matrix categorized studies by analyzing them and recording key information in a spreadsheet. This approach made it easier to compare studies and draw higher-level conclusions. The studies mainly focused on three main areas: the impact of AI on organizational performance, the adoption and use of AI in organizations, and the organizational changes resulting from AI adoption.

Fig 1. Study Selection Process

The data recorded included research methods, important definitions, levels of analysis, key findings, theories used, contexts of investigation, and other significant concepts. Data extraction was guided by the concept matrix and refined through an iterative process. Researchers reached

consensus on how to categorize each study and added new dimensions to ensure all relevant data was captured. In total, 45 studies were analyzed and added to the matrix before synthesizing the findings.

Table 1. Keywords Used During Selection Process ^[24]

No.	Thematic Category	Keywords
1	AI technologies	Artificial intelligence, cognitive technology, robotic automation, cognitive insight, process automation, machine learning, deep learning, cognitive automation, neural network, supervised learning, unsupervised learning, natural language processing, computer vision, machine vision, expert systems, cognitive application, image recognition, reinforcement learning, deep mind technologies, adaptive algorithms, recurrent neural networks, machine perception, machine intelligence, heuristic search techniques, decision tree, data mining, convolutional neural network, cluster analysis, classification, chatbots, autonomous computing, semantic analysis, image recognition, simulation intelligence, challenges of AI, integrate AI, cost of AI, deployment of AI, AI and big data, influence of AI, AI transformation,
2	Organizational	Business value, organisational challenges, organisational opportunities, adoption, business benefits, business process redesign, organisational change, firm performance, organisational performance, competitive advantage, process innovation, business transformation, business process management, digital transformation, business strategy, business gains, business performance, cognitive engagement, business opportunities, transformation process, business activities, data-driven decisions, competitive performance, business efficiency, reduce business costs, business management, business decision, business challenges, commercial value, business value proposition, business growth, business success, customer value, customer fragmentation, customer, service, corporate value, leadership,

4. KEY FINDINGS OF STUDY

Based on the literature survey performed the key findings of the study have been summarized below:

- **Use of AI**

AI has a wide range of applications across various fields, including marketing, enterprise management, production management and customer services extending throughout the entire value chain of an organization to transform processes and enhance efficiency while revolutionizing key aspects of daily life. Broadly AI

applications are categorized into automation which replaces human tasks with accurate, efficient AI systems and augmentation which enhances the human intelligence by providing deep insights for better decision making.

Automation is evident in domains like customer service chatbots, robotic applications while focusing on task efficiency and overall productivity whereas augmentation includes AI-driven analytics platforms and virtual assistants that support strategy development and task management. Both automation and augmentation

not only streamline internal processes and workflows but also improve customer experiences with innovative products and services such as recommendation engines in e-commerce or diagnostic tools in healthcare. By integrating these approaches, organizations balance efficiency with innovation ensuring competitiveness in a dynamic business environment.

- **Impact of AI**

The question of how AI contributes to achieve competitive performance is of great concern for the global business leaders. To address this, it is important to analyze the impacts of AI in two distinct levels: first process level effects (1st order impacts) and second firm level outcomes (2nd order impacts). At the process level understanding of how AI transforms individual business processes is important. This includes examining how automation, data analysis, and AI-driven insights improve efficiency, accuracy, and decision-making.

At the firm level these transformed processes collectively drive larger strategic advantages such as innovation, market responsiveness, and improved customer satisfaction which ultimately lead to sustain competitive performance. The following subsections discuss first and second order effects of AI while exploring the relationship between AI enabled process, collective improvements and their implications for organizational success.

- **1st order impacts:**

Initial impact of AI is most evident at the organizational' process level where it drives significant variations in operation and overall performance. Key performance indicators (KPIs) such as effectiveness, efficiency, productivity, capacity, profitability, quality, value and competitiveness are commonly used to assess the improvements and monitor the organizational output. AI greatly influences process in three primary ways including reduction of resource wastage, efficiency enhancement by automating tasks and optimizing the workflows thus generating the deep actionable insights through advanced data analysis to support the informed decision making and transforming the business

productivity by introducing innovative models and adaptability. Collectively these effects not only enhance the operational performance but also enable the organization to embrace consistent innovation and deliver more valuable outcomes.

- **2nd order impacts:**

The second order impacts of AI extend beyond the individual processes to influence the firm level outcomes thus shaping the various dimensions of organizational performance. These key effects can be divided into four key areas. 1st operational performance which improves as AI greatly influences the agility, efficiency and collective effectiveness of operations across the firm. 2nd accounting performance which benefits through revenue growth, cost optimization and enhanced financial reporting accuracy driven by the analytical capabilities of AI models. 3rd is the market based performance which is supported by the role of AI in enhancing the market competitiveness, expansion of market reach and enabling the customer centric innovations. Finally the 4th dimension is sustainability performance which is greatly influenced as AI supports long term social & environmental goals, promotes eco friendly practices and enhance resource efficiency. Collectively these firm level impacts of AI unveil the transformative potential of AI in fostering the resilience and overall business growth.

- **Role of AI in Reshaping the Reptation of Organization**

The organizational reputation is closely linked to the trust it manages to earn from its' customers and other stakeholders which directly influence its' financial performance. The adoption of AI technologies can greatly influence the overall trust levels among the key entities such as business partners and customers. However published literature also suggests that for an organization to completely rely on AI's outcomes it must incorporate technical experts which may guide that how these AI models actually operate, how the reliability and safe usage of AI systems can be ensured. Consequently, prior to implementation of AI systems an organization must prioritize transparency by clearly communicating the

technical features of AI and its dependability. It can significantly contribute to built an utmost trust of stakeholders in an organization which is crucial to maintain the overall market reputation.

5. CONCLUSION

AI plays a crucial transformative role in the business decision making by enhancing the overall operational efficiency, generating thorough actionable insights and innovation. It increases the organizational capacity to improve the performance parameters and optimize the process across multiple dimensions to comply the competitive market and customer demands. However the successful integration of AI demands deep attention to ensure the transparency of outcomes as it greatly impacts the relationship of stakeholders and organizational reputation. By responsibly strategically incorporating the AI business can achieve their complete potential to improve market competitiveness, financial growth and long term sustainability. AI is a continuously evolving technology that's why understanding its' impacts on business communication, cultural perceptions, and customer trust can critically maximize its' worth in decision making and fostering the positive image of an organization.

6. FUTURE SCOPE

Future studies could explore how AI affects trust, its impact on organizational reputation, and the factors influencing trust formation, including the technical attributes of AI, communication strategies, and cultural variations in perceptions of AI applications.

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